

Renoprotection in diabetic nephropathy by chlorogenic acid from *Sargassum ilicifolium* extract through SIRT1 interaction

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Abstract

Diabetic nephropathy is a major complication of type 2 diabetes mellitus, and current therapies are limited by their lack of efficacy and adverse effects. Marine algae are a rich source of bioactive metabolites with potential nephroprotective activity. The present study evaluated the nephroprotective effects of *Sargassum ilicifolium* extract using *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches. Ethanolic extract was characterized by UV-Visible spectroscopy, FTIR, NMR, and LC–MS analyses, which revealed phenolic acids and sterols, and the most prominent bioactive constituent is chlorogenic acid. In HK-2 cells, MTT assay show that chlorogenic acid shows an IC₅₀ of ~238 µg/mL. Docking studies confirmed strong binding interaction of chlorogenic acid to SIRT1 (–5.85 kcal/mol). Collectively, these findings indicate that chlorogenic acid isolated from *S. ilicifolium* extract exhibits nephroprotective activity through interaction with SIRT1 and increases its activation thereby serves as a potential natural therapeutic candidate for diabetic nephropathy.

Keywords: *Sargassum ilicifolium*, Nephroprotection, SIRT1, chlorogenic acid

1. Introduction

Diabetes mellitus, is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia resulting from impaired insulin secretion, action, or both [1]. Persistent elevated blood glucose levels in diabetes result in numerous biochemical and structural alterations across various organs, resulting in microvascular and macrovascular complications. Among the microvascular complications, three primary conditions collectively called "three pathies" are diabetic nephropathy (renal damage) [2], diabetic retinopathy (retinal damage) [3], and diabetic neuropathy (nerve damage) [4].

Diabetic nephropathy is a disorder characterized by multifactorial molecular mechanisms, which trigger the persistent hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, inflammation, and fibrosis [5]. The progression of the disease follows well-defined stages: an initial hyperfiltration phase with an increased glomerular filtration rate (GFR), succeeded by microalbuminuria (an early indicator of renal injury), overt proteinuria, and ultimately a decline in renal function, leading to chronic kidney disease and end-stage renal disease (ESRD). The pathogenesis of diabetic nephropathy involves multiple factors, including persistent hyperglycemia-induced oxidative stress, overproduction of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), activation of the renin–angiotensin–aldosterone system (RAAS), podocyte injury, mesangial expansion, thickening of the glomerular basement membrane (GBM), and chronic low-grade inflammation [6]. The inflammatory mediators such as nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B), tumour necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) exacerbate renal damage, leading to fibrosis and impaired renal function [7].

Sirtuin 1 (SIRT1), a NAD⁺-dependent histone deacetylase [8], has been identified as an important therapeutic target in diabetic nephropathy. SIRT1 confers renal protection by deacetylating and regulating various transcription factors, and co-activators, including NF- κ B, FOXO, and PGC-1 α [9]. Through these mechanisms, SIRT1 mitigates oxidative stress, curtails pro-inflammatory cytokine production, enhances mitochondrial biogenesis, promotes autophagy, and combats kidney fibrosis. Animal studies utilizing SIRT1 activators, such as resveratrol, have demonstrated a significant reduction in renal injury in diabetic models, showing their therapeutic potential [10].

Brown seaweeds, particularly *Sargassum illicifolium* [11], found in tropical and subtropical waters, have been traditionally used in various cultures for their medicinal properties. Chemical analyses have identified a diverse array of active compounds, including sulphated polysaccharides (fucoidans), polyphenols (phlorotannins), sterols (fucosterol), pigments (fucoxanthin), and minerals [12]. These compounds have exhibited antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-obesity, anti-hypertensive, and anti-diabetic effects in laboratory studies. Polysaccharides from *S. illicifolium* are particularly effective in scavenging free radicals and inhibiting α -glucosidase, while phlorotannins and fucosterol demonstrate anti-inflammatory and cholesterol-lowering properties [13]. The polysaccharides from *S. illicifolium* possess strong free-radical scavenging and α -glucosidase inhibitory activities, while phlorotannins and fucosterol exhibit anti-inflammatory and lipid-lowering properties. These bioactivities suggest that *S. illicifolium* could serve as a complementary or supplementary therapy to mitigate diabetic complications, including nephropathy, potentially through pathways involving SIRT1. *Sargassum illicifolium* serves as a supportive or adjunct treatment for managing diabetic

complications, particularly nephropathy, by acting through mechanisms that may intersect with SIRT1-regulated pathways. This research explores combating diabetic nephropathy by activating SIRT1 and by utilizing the bioactive compounds of *Sargassum ilicifolium*, with the aim of reducing renal cell damage to slow or reverse disease progression.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection of *Sargassum ilicifolium*

Fresh samples of the brown alga *Sargassum ilicifolium* were collected from the intertidal zone near Rameswaram, Tamil Nadu, India (9.2876° N, 79.3173° E) during low tide. The algae were harvested and washed initially with seawater, and then repeatedly with distilled water to remove epiphytes, sand, and debris. The cleaned biomass was shade-dried at ambient temperature for 4-5 days to conserve the thermolabile constituents and subsequently ground into a fine powder.

2.2. Preparation of *Sargassum ilicifolium* extract

For the efficient extraction of bioactive components from the algal biomass, ethanol is used as a suitable solvent as it has the ability to solubilize a wide range of metabolites. Approximately 250 g of dried powder of *S. ilicifolium* was extracted with 2500 mL of ethanol with a sample-to-solvent ratio of 1:10 (w/v) for 48 hours with intermittent stirring. After 48 hours, Soxhlet extraction was performed. The filtrate was then concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator, followed by drying at 40 °C to remove residual solvent. This process resulted in 12.5 g of crude ethanolic extract, corresponding to a 5% yield, and is stored in air-tight amber vials at 4 °C for further experimental purposes [14].

2.3. Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC-MS)

The phytochemical constituents present in the ethanolic extract of *S. ilicifolium* were identified by performing LC-MS analysis. The ethanolic extract was filtered through a 0.2 µm membrane disk, and the filtrate was used for the LC-MS analysis. About 10 µL of the sample was injected into an Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC) system equipped with an ACQUITY UPLC-BEH C18 reverse-phase column. Separation was performed with the mobile phase that comprises formic acid and acetonitrile. Other mass spectrometric parameters were capillary voltage at 4000 V, and nitrogen gas at 35 psi. The mass spectral data acquisition was attained under positive electrospray ionization (ESI). The fragments produced were identified using the available library of molecules, and the phytoconstituents in the extract were detected based on their based on m/z values.

2.4. Isolation of Chlorogenic Acid by Column Chromatography

The ethanolic extract of the *S. ilicifolium* was dried and then dissolved in methanol and adsorbed on the silica gel (100-200 mesh) and allowed to evaporate. The dried material is now loaded onto a silica gel column, which has already been packed with hexane as a mobile phase. Elution was performed with increasing polarity of solvents, namely petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, chloroform and methanol. Initially, different ratio of petroleum ether and ethyl acetate is used (95:5, 90:10, 85:15, 80:20, 75:25, 70:30, 65:35, 60:40, 50:50, 40:60, 30:70, 20:80, and 10:90) with 100% of ethyl acetate as the final elution. Followed by this, the column is then eluted with an ethyl acetate and chloroform mixture in the same ratio as discussed earlier, with

100 % chloroform in the final elution. Finally, a chloroform and methanol mixture is used for the elution. A total of 104 fractions is obtained at the end and each fraction was analysed using thin-layer chromatography (TLC). Fractions 84 to 92 show similar R_f values and these fractions were combined and concentrated under reduced pressure to obtain crude material.

The purification of the crude material was carried out by treatment with activated charcoal in the presence of hot ethanol. The solution is filtered and the filtrate obtained was kept under refrigerated conditions for crystallization. A yellow color solid was obtained, which was then subjected to additional structural and spectral characterization studies using UV-Visible spectrophotometry, proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H-NMR), and carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance (¹³C-NMR) spectroscopy, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and mass spectrometry (MS).

2.5. Spectral Characterization

2.5.1. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

For FTIR analysis, sample is prepared by grinding the yellow solid product into fine powder and nearly 2mg of the sample was mixed with about 200 mg of potassium bromide (KBr). The mixture is again ground to attain a homogenous mixture with below 2 μm of particle size, which is then compressed in a hydraulic press to a transparent pellet. Perkin Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer 1650 was used for the FTIR analysis, and the readings were measured with the mid-infrared range between 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹.

2.5.2. Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy

The structure of the isolated compound was determined using ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic studies and analysis was performed on a Bruker Avance 400 MHz spectrometer, which operates at 400 MHz and 100 MHz, respectively. About 5 to 20 mg of the sample was dissolved in 0.5 to 0.7 mL of DMSO and analyzed in the spectrometer. Chemical shifts (δ) were given in parts per million (ppm) relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard and the Coupling constants (J) were given in hertz (Hz).

2.5.3. Mass Spectroscopy

The isolated phytoconstituent were dissolved in analytical grade acetonitrile or methanol and filtered through a 0.2 μm membrane filter, and the filtrate was used for mass spectra analysis in a JEOL-Accu TOF JMS-T100 LC Mass spectrometer. Data acquisition and processing were carried out using the manufacturer's software to ensure reproducibility and analytical reliability.

2.6. MTT assay

The cell viability of the isolated compound in HK-2 cells was assessed using the MTT assay. The cells were initially seeded in a 96-well plate with each well containing the cell density of × 10³ cells/well (100 μL) and incubated at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ for 24 hours. Then, these cells were treated with varying concentrations of chlorogenic acid (50, 100, 200, 400 and 800 μg/mL) and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. Cells without any treatment serve as the control group. After incubation, the cells were treated with 20 μL of MTT reagent and allowed to stand for 3 to 4 hours. At the end of incubation, the MTT reagent was discarded, and the purple colored formazan crystals that were produced by the metabolically active cells were dissolved

by the addition of 150 μ L of DMSO. The absorbance of each well was measured at 570nm in a microplate reader. The cell viability percentage was calculated with respect to the control group and the experiment was performed in triplicate for reproducibility. A graph is plotted with the concentration of the chlorogenic acid along the x-axis and the percentage of cytotoxicity along the y-axis. From the graph, the IC₅₀ value of Chlorogenic acid was calculated [15].

2.7. Molecular docking

Molecular Docking was performed using Auto Dock Vina involving SIRT1 (PDB ID: 5BTR) [16]. First, the crystal structures of the protein was downloaded from the Protein Data Bank and prepared by removing water molecules and co-crystallized ligands, adding polar hydrogens, assigning Gasteiger charges, and saving it in PDBQT format using Auto Dock Tools (ADT). Chlorogenic acid was obtained from the PubChem database, energy minimized using the MMFF94 force field in Avogadro software. Grid box for SIRT1 was centered around the NAD⁺ or inhibitor binding site, guided by coordinates of the co-crystallized ligands. Docking was performed using AutoDock Vina and the output gives the information on different binding poses and binding affinities. The resulting complexes are analysed using molecular visualization tools like PyMOL to interpret binding modes, interaction types, and docking scores.

3.Result

3.1. LC-MS Analysis

The results of the LC-MS analysis of the ethanolic extract of *S. illicifolium* were given in the table 1. The chromatogram of the extract is given in Figure 1 with its retention time and intensity of these phytochemicals. Various alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, and polyphenols were found to be present in the extract. Some of the notable phytochemicals include quercetin, kaempferol, luteolin, apigenin, naringenin, ferulic acid, gallic acid, caffeic acid, coumaric acid, etc. Among these phytoconstituents, one of the key phytochemicals found is chlorogenic acid with m/z of 354.31 and RT of 4.5 minutes, exhibiting a high degree of similarity in RT (retention time) and spectral similarity scores, which aligns with the compounds deposited in the libraries.

Table 1: Compounds identified in the ethanolic extract of *S. illicifolium* by LC-MS

S. No.	Compound Name	Class	Mol. Formula	Mol. Wt. (Da)	Peak Match (%)	RT
Alkaloids						
1	Trigonelline	Alkaloid	C ₇ H ₇ NO ₂	137.05	99.4	1.88
2	Salsolinol	Alkaloid	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NO ₂	179.09	99.5	2.80
3	DL-Stachydrine	Alkaloid	C ₇ H ₁₃ NO ₂	143.09	99.0	2.46
4	3-Pyridylacetic acid	Alkaloid-related	C ₇ H ₇ NO ₂	137.05	98.9	8.2
5	NP-019811	Alkaloid-like	C ₆ H ₇ NO ₂	125.05	99.8	2.1
Glycosides						
6	D-(+)-Maltose	Glycoside	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₁	342.12	99.5	2.88
7	(2R,3R,4S,5S,6R)-oxane-triol derivative	Glycoside	C ₁₆ H ₂₈ O ₇	332.18	99.8	3.18
8	NP-013538	Glycoside-like	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₈	288.08	99.1	3.5
10	Glucoside derivative (reported fragment)	Glycoside	–	–	–	3.7
Flavonoids						
11	Quercetin	Flavonoid	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	302.24	–	6.1
12	Kaempferol	Flavonoid	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	286.24	–	9.1
13	Luteolin	Flavonoid	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	286.24	–	5.5
14	Apigenin	Flavonoid	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	270.24	–	8
15	Naringenin	Flavonoid	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₅	272.25	–	5.5
Polyphenols						
16	Chlorogenic acid	Polyphenol	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₉	354.31	>99	4.5
17	Caffeic acid	Polyphenol	C ₉ H ₈ O ₄	180.16	–	3.8
18	Ferulic acid	Polyphenol	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄	194.18	–	4.3
19	Gallic acid	Polyphenol	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅	170.12	–	3.2
20	p-Coumaric acid	Polyphenol	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃	164.16	–	4.8

Figure 1: LC-MS chromatogram of *Sargassum ilicifolium*

3.2. Characterization of Chlorogenic Acid

3.2.1. FTIR

The FTIR spectrum of chlorogenic acid showed characteristic peaks that define the functional groups in it (Figure 2). Bands at 3468 cm^{-1} and 3323 cm^{-1} correspond to the O–H stretching vibrations, which indicate the presence of hydroxyl groups of phenolic and carboxylic acid moieties. Peaks at 2968 cm^{-1} and 2842 cm^{-1} confer for the =CH stretching vibrations, corresponding to the vinyl groups in the caffeic acid. A band at 1685 cm^{-1} is for the carbonyl (C=O) stretching of the ester and carboxyl groups. The aromatic C=C stretching displays a peak at 1441 cm^{-1} . Additionally, a distinct peak at 1286 cm^{-1} reflects the –CH bending vibrations. This confirms that the isolated compound is chlorogenic acid (Figure 3).

Figure 2: IR spectrum of Chlorogenic acid

Figure 3: Structure of Chlorogenic acid

3.2.2. NMR

¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): A downfield singlet at δ 12.40 ppm corresponds to the carboxylic acid proton (-COOH) and two singlets at δ 9.58 and 9.14 ppm, which correspond to aromatic hydroxyl (-OH) protons. The resonance in the aromatic region was between δ 6.97–7.43 ppm, which suggests doublets at 7.03 ppm and 7.39–7.43 ppm, and a multiplet at 6.97–6.99 ppm. Quinic acid moiety's protons attached with the hydroxylated carbons were seen at δ 4.76 and 5.08 ppm, while additional hydroxyl protons appeared as singlets at δ 3.56, 3.92, and 5.59 ppm for the aliphatic region. Multiplets between δ 1.75 and 2.04 ppm confer for its aliphatic protons in the quinic ring (Figure 4(a-c)).

Figure 4(a-c): ^1H -NMR spectrum of Chlorogenic acid

The ^{13}C -NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6): The resonance at δ 174.94 ppm corresponds to the carboxylic acid carbon (C7). The aromatic carbons comprising hydroxyl groups were confirmed by the signals δ 165.72, 148.35, 145.56, and 144.96 ppm, which suggests the presence of phenolic hydroxyl groups. Resonance between δ 114.28 and 125.60 ppm suggests the substituted benzene structure. Downfield signals at δ 73.44, 70.89, 70.32, 68.01 ppm confer for the hydroxylated aliphatic carbons in the quinic acid ring. Resonances at δ 37.20 and 36.19 ppm represented methylene carbons (Figure 5(a-c)).

Figure 5(a-c): ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of Chlorogenic acid

3.2.3. Mass Spectroscopy

The molecular weight of the isolated compound was determined by mass spectrometry (Figure 6). The mass spectrum showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 355.0, which represents the protonated molecular ion ($M+1$) of chlorogenic acid. This aligns with the molecular weight of chlorogenic acid, which is 354.31 g/mol. Thus, the isolated compound is of high purity and confirmed to be chlorogenic acid.

Figure 6: Mass spectrum of Chlorogenic acid

3.4. MTT Assay

The cytotoxic effect of chlorogenic acid in HK-2 cells, analysed by MTT assay, is given in Figure 8 and 9. There is an increase in the cytotoxic effect of chlorogenic acid with an increase in the concentration. 15% of cytotoxicity was seen at 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and up to 80% at 800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The IC50 value was found to be 238 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, and this shows that chlorogenic is safe when administered at low doses.

Figure 7: Cell Viability of different concentrations of Chlorogenic acid in HK-2 Cells

Figure 8: Cytotoxicity percentage of different concentrations of Chlorogenic acid in HK-2 Cells

3.5. Molecular Docking

In a molecular docking study, chlorogenic acid was evaluated for its binding affinity with SIRT1 (PDB ID: 5BTR). Chlorogenic acid exhibited a binding energy of -5.85 kcal/mol, indicative of a weaker interaction at the NAD^+ /inhibitor binding site of the deacetylase (Figure 9a and b and Table 2 and 3). These suggest that chlorogenic acid has a higher affinity and likely a more effective inhibitory action to SIRT1 [16].

Figure 9(a and b): 2D and 3D interaction between Chlorogenic acid and the binding site residues of human SIRT1 (PDB ID:5BTR)

Table 2. Molecular docking of Chlorogenic acid with SIRT1 protein

Target (PDB ID)	Compound (Pubchem)	Name of the Compound	Binding energy (kcal/mol)	Predicted inhibitory constant value
human SIRT1 (PDB ID:5BTR)	1794427	Chlorogenic acid	-5.85	51.86 μ M

Table 3 : Summary of molecular interactions between Chlorogenic acid and the binding site residues of human SIRT1

S. No.	Interaction Type	Binding Residues
1	Hydrophobic interactions	F414, V445, P212, A295
2	Hydrophilic interaction	E214, D292, D298, Q294, E208, K444
3	Hydrogen bond interactions	E214, D298, K444
4	π - π interactions	F414 (with aromatic ring of ligand)
5	Cation- π interactions	K444, R446 (likely candidates)

4. Discussion

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by increased blood glucose level for a long period of time resulting from impaired insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. Uncontrolled diabetes leads to various complications and one of the serious complications is diabetic nephropathy, a progressive kidney disease. Diabetic nephropathy typically onset as proteinuria, which gradually leads to a lowering of renal function and finally to end-stage renal disease if untreated [17]. *Sargassum ilicifolium* is highly prevalent in the tropical Pacific region and the Indian Ocean region. Various studies have reported its biological activities, such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, etc [18]. LC-MS analysis revealed the presence of numerous bioactive constituents in the extract. The presence of chlorogenic acid in the seaweed was reported in previous studies [19].

The characterization of chlorogenic acid was performed using FTIR, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, and mass spectrometry analyses. The FTIR spectrum exhibited peaks corresponding to hydroxyl groups (3468 and 3323 cm⁻¹), vinyl =CH stretches (2968 and 2842 cm⁻¹), carbonyl (C=O) group at 1685 cm⁻¹, aromatic double bonds at 1441 cm⁻¹, and -CH bending at 1286 cm⁻¹, which is similar to the already reported literature studies. The ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR resonances' chemical shifts match those of chlorogenic acid. Mass spectrometry revealed the molecular ion peak at m/z 355.0 (M+1), validating compound identity and purity [20], [21], [22].

SIRT1 protein plays a major role in the regulation of metabolic stress, thereby preventing oxidative stress, apoptosis and inflammation in renal cells. Persistent hyperglycemia in diabetic nephropathy conditions affects the expression of SIRT1 protein, thereby resulting in the onset of renal injury. Chlorogenic acid from *S. ilicifolium* increases the expression of SIRT1, thereby mitigating the onset of renal injury. SIRT1 activation deacetylates FOXO and PGC-1 α , thereby increasing the antioxidant mechanism and mitochondrial biogenesis and inhibiting the NF- κ B signaling [23]. The docking interaction of SIRT1 with chlorogenic acid shows a binding energy of -5.85 kcal/mol. The interaction analysis revealed that chlorogenic acid is stabilized by Glu214, Asp292, Asp298, Ala295, Gln294, Thr209, Lys444, Arg446, Phe414, Pro212, and Val445 at SIRT1 protein. These residues, through hydrogen bonds and polar or hydrophobic contacts, anchor the ligand within the binding site. This suggests chlorogenic acid exhibit its interaction with SIRT1 [16].

5. Conclusion:

This study demonstrates the nephroprotective role of chlorogenic acid, as one of the chief bioactive constituents in *S. ilicifolium*, exhibit good interaction with SIRT1, a key regulator involved in cellular stress responses and renal protection. These findings show that the use of *S. ilicifolium* as a promising natural agent for protecting renal function and mitigating diabetic kidney damage, with chlorogenic acid and SIRT1 modulation being the central mechanism.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

Ramya involves in Conceptualization, Literature collection and writing. Rahul contributes for the complete Manuscript design and final draft preparation.

All the authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interests.

CONSENT STATEMENT

Not applicable. No human participants, personal data, or identifiable images were used in this study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The animal experiments were approved by the ethical committee of the institute.

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